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Economic Hardship and Educational Administration in Nigeria: Implication for Decision Making for Sustainable Education Development

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Annotation: This paper assessed the impact of economic hardship on education in Nigeria. Secondary data were used to support every point raised in the paper. The secondary data were collected from print and online publications. Content analysis was employed to narrow the literature to the areas of theme. The paper concluded that economic hardship in Nigeria has affected educational administration in Nigeria by increasing the operational costs of running educational institutions across the country. The paper disclosed that economic hardship has affected the running of schools, led to a drop in budgetary allocation to schools, led to a reduction in the provision of educational resources, affected recruitment of teachers, students' enrolment in schools, quality of education and infrastructure facilities development in schools across the country. Based on the findings of this study, the paper recommends that: Governments should diversify the economy by increasing local production and providing tax holidays for schools and private investors. Governments should provide loan facilities for private schools. Governments should provide palliative for underprivileged Nigerians to enable them to support the schooling of their wards.

Keywords: Educational Administration, Economic Hardship, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION(KIRISH)

The responsibility for administering the education sector in Nigeria is shared among the federal, state and local governments. Thus, in the country's constitution, education is on the concurrent list, but the Federal Government is empowered to regulate all its sectors, engage in policy formation and ensure quality control. Also, the provisions of the constitution allow each tier of government to focus its responsibilities mainly on a sector of education. The Federal Government is involved directly in tertiary education. The states take care of secondary education, while the local governments handle primary education. Despite this arrangement, the Federal Government is expected to support the state and local governments in counterpart funding to enhance the quality of education in the country (NEEDS, 2014).

The administration of the education system is shared mainly among the education ministries at the federal and state levels, as well as statutory bodies referred to as commissions. There are commissions established for different subsectors of the education system and are charged with various responsibilities for the subsectors. The FME is responsible for the coherence of the national policy and procedures and for ensuring that the states' policies operate within the parameters of the national policy as adapted for local needs (Moja, 2000). Coordination of policy at the political level is handled by the National Council of Education, the highest policymaking body chaired by the Federal Minister of Education and includes all the State Commissioners of Education. This body is advised by the Joint Consultative Committee on Education, which consists of all the Federal and State Directors of Education, Chief Executives of education statutory bodies, and Directors of University Institutes of Education (NEEDS, 2014).

The state-level education ministries are responsible for the development and implementation of educational policies, management and supervision of educational institutions in their respective states. Specifically, the responsibilities for maintaining all public elementary and secondary schools are vested in the education ministry. Such responsibilities include: determining the salaries of teachers; recruitment, appointment, promotion and discipline of staff; and provision of guidelines on the establishment of new schools and training and re-training of teaching and non-teaching staff. The oversight functions of the Ministry of Education are carried out through several agencies. For instance, the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) is responsible for the management of basic education, while the Teaching Service Commission takes charge of senior secondary education at the state level (NEEDS, 2014).

Tertiary education is under the supervision of commissions set up by law and which operate as parastatals of the FME. For instance, universities are supervised by the NUC, while colleges of education are supervised by the NCCE. The NBTE oversees polytechnic education. These commissions are responsible for policy decisions affecting institutions under their supervision, maintenance of standards through a system of periodic accreditation of courses, distribution and monitoring of government funding, the appointment of members of governing councils, and the day-to-day running of the

institutions (NEEDS, 2014). Educational administration in Nigeria appears to be threatened by the economic hardship Nigeria as a country is facing. The impact of the economic hardship in Nigeria is multifaceted as it cuts across all institutions of the nation. Social institutions are interconnected and interdependent as each sector affects the other positively or negatively. The current economic hardship has its toll on educational institutions as both parents and students are victims of the economic recession (Komolafe, 2016). It is based on this that this paper aimed to assess the impact of economic hardship on educational administration in Nigeria with a focus on

Concept of Educational Administration

Educational administration is the application of educational resources to achieve educational goals. Educational administration is the act and process of using resources in effective and efficient ways to attain the various objectives of educational institutions. Educational administration deals with the planning and organizing of human and material resources to realise the goals of educational institutions. Educational administration is the systematic arrangement of educational input in an operational means to achieve the set goals of educational institutions (Ogunode, 2020a). Educational administration is concerned with integrating the appropriate human and material resources that are made available and effective for achieving the purposes of a program of an educational institution (Nwiyi, 2018). Educational administration is the process of identifying, mobilizing and utilizing scarce human and material resources relevant to education to achieve specific educational goals efficiently and effectively (Osai & Kalagbor, 2017).

Educational administration according to Okoroma, (2016) is the process that involves a careful and systematic use of methods, principles, plans and procedures necessary to achieve the educational objectives. The objectives of educational administration according to Okoroma, (2016) as follows: (1) to provide proper education to students, (2) to ensure adequate utilization of all resources, (3) to ensure professional ethics and professional development among teachers, (4) to organize educational programmes for acquainting students with the art of democratic living and giving them excellent training in democratic citizenship, (5) to mobilize the community, (6) to organize co-curricular activities effectively for developing talents of students and work efficiency of educational teachers, (7) to get the work done, (8) to prepare students for taking their places in various vocations and avenues of life, (9) to train the students in developing scientific attitude and objective outlook among them towards all aspects and activities of life, and (10) to ensure qualitative improvement of education.

Educational administration is designed to involve many programmes of activities. Kalagbor (2017) stated that the following activities and programmes come under the scope of educational administration at the institutional level: (a) Deciding the purposes

of the institution or school,(b) Planning for academic or curricular and co-curricular activities,(c) Preparing the time table and the time schedules for various activities,(d) Assigning duties and responsibilities to the staff members,(e) Organizing curricular and co-curricular programmes, (f) Directing and motivating the staff of the institution, (g) Coordinating by efforts of people to achieve the purpose. h. Exercising control over the staff,(i) Conducting periodical reviews about the progress, achievements and failures of the institution,(j) Taking measures for staff development,(k) Maintaining order and discipline,(l) Management of materials(m) Management of finance(n) Maintaining records and registers up to date, (o)Maintaining human relationships,(p) Supervision of the work of teachers and other employees(q) Giving feedback to the teachers performing well and taking remedial measures for teachers not performing well. The educational administration programme and activities appear to be affected by the economic hardship in Nigeria that is caused by inflation and other economic problems.

Concept of Economic Hardship

Economic hardship has been conceptualized by different scholars such as Kraus and Park (2014), they defined hardship as contrasted with poverty, which is simply the lack of economic resources while economic hardship does not need to involve an actual lack of economic resources, but simply a perception of this deficit. Economic perceptions are heavily influenced by comparative processes. Economic hardship is viewed by Fenny (2022) as the inability to meet reasonable basic living expenses is caused by many factors. Economic hardship is defined as "a significant decline in economic activity spread across the economy, lasting for a while, normally visible in real Gross Domestic Product (GDP), real income, employment, industrial production (National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER, 2012).

Economic hardship and economic activities decreasesubstantially, and the decline affects wide portions of the economy and it has some permanence (Sabitu, 2023). Ogunode, Afolabi and Daniel (2024) defined economic hardship as an economic situation whereby there are difficulties faced by individuals, institutions and organisations due to income loss, unemployment, job instability, and economic insecurity. Economic hardship can also be seen as an economic condition that is characterized by inflation, high unemployment, high debt rate, low income and reduced standard of living of the people. Economic hardship is a condition of economic meltdown where citizens of a country cannot afford their basic needs due to inflation and a high rate of unemployment that is caused by bad leadership, corruption and unstable economic policies. The indicators of economic hardship include a high rate of unemployment, inflation, debt rate, poor exchange rate, high rate of poverty among citizens and low income (Ogunode, et al 2024). Economic hardship according to Ogunode, Olofinkua, & Sunmonu, (2024) is an economic activities that is constantly decrease and the decline affects wide economic activities which leads to inflation, unemployment and high standard of living among the citizens. Economic hardship also implies an economic situation that whereby citizens of a country

cannot afford to meet up with their economic need as a result of inflation unemployment, high debt burden, low direct investment and high poverty.

Impact of Economic Hardship on Educational Administration in Nigeria

Educational administration has many functions in the school system. For this paper, the core functions of educational administration will be limited to budgetary allocation to schools, provision of educational resources, recruitment of teachers, ensuring constant student enrolment in schools, ensuring the quality of education and ensuring infrastructure facilities development.

Budgetary allocation to schools

Educational administration ensures proper school budgeting for effective school operation and implementation of school programmes. Economic hardship in Nigeria has affected school budgeting. It appears that both public and private school budgets were cut down due to the economic crisis in the country. Bamigboye, Ede and Adeyemi (2016) investigated how the economic crisis affected schooling in Southwest Nigeria. According to the survey data gathered, the current economic crisis in Nigeria had a noticeable effect on the education industry as several state governments went on to make significant budget cuts in this area. The study's findings indicate a difference between states that cut education spending due to the economy or a financial crisis and those that increase funding for the sector during those times. According to the study's findings, the economic downturn in Southwestern Nigeria has hurt schooling. Schady (2004) observed that in an attempt to survive, the burden of governance is transferred to the poor masses as some state governments embarked on overall budget cuts to avoid the consequences of the recession and as a result monies that were initially supposed to be channelled to education sector were reduced drastically leading to a reduction in school enrolment, especially private schools, given the decline in household and public incomes. Inflation which is one of the indicators of economic hardship has affected the budgetary allocation to education according to the World Bank (2018). This reduction in the budgetary allocation has affected the procurement of educational resources, employment of teachers and starting and completion of new infrastructure facilities projects in educational institutions. Even though it has been noted that fund is the lifeblood of any human society (Ayeni, 2017). The research carried out by Adegoke (2011) titled *The Impact of Inflation on the Quality of Education in Nigeria* found that the government has not provided enough funds to improve the quality of education due to the economic crisis of inflation. The funds that are expected to be provided by the government for the effective running of the education sector have not been provided. This above is the reason why scholars have argued that when a structure is not performing its function optimally (Joseph, Cinjel & Ayeni, 2017). Consequent upon the foregoing, Obiakor (2021) has contended that economic recession has caused unemployment, lower wages, high taxation, budget deficit, rising bond yields and untold hardship on the people to a great extent and propelled Poor quality and ineffective teaching in secondary schools to a great extent.

Provision of educational resources

One of the core functions of educational administration is to ensure the provision of adequate educational resources supply to schools to support the implementation of school programmes. The economic hardship in Nigeria today seems to have affected the rate at which school administration procures and supplies teachers and non-teaching staff resources to carry out their functions. The economic hardship that is centred more on inflation has reduced the volume of funds available for school operation and this directly affected the purchasing power of the schools in the areas of provision of instruction resources and others. The teaching materials' costs increased as a result of the economic downturn. Given the high foreign currency rate brought on by the poor economic conditions, the high cost of teaching supplies and equipment keeps them out of the grasp of the majority of institutions (Echor & Lohor, 2022). The decrease in budgetary support for education, which is mostly attributable to the economic downturn according to Schady (2004), has a severe impact on the provision of school facilities, money for education, and the working conditions of teachers, students, and families. Nwankwo (2018) carried out a study titled *Inflation and Education in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria*. The findings of this study revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between inflation and education. The study also revealed that inflation hurts the quality of education. It was also found that inflation hurts the availability of educational resources, such as classroom space and textbooks. The study also revealed that inflation hurts the level of teachers' salaries, which in turn affects the quality of education. Yenle (2017) stated that it is also obvious that the government is affected by the same crisis as they have trouble disbursing grants, paying worker's compensation, buying books, subscribing to journals needed for effective delivery of the curriculum, training staff at workshops, conferences, and seminars, as well as keeping up with the rate of renovation of dilapidated buildings.

Recruitment of teachers

Educational administration ensures the effective recruitment of teachers to schools to ensure the attainment of quality education. The economic hardship in Nigeria has affected the recruitment of teachers into schools especially in private institutions rather than stay in business, school administrators downsized their labour force. Anele (2020) conducted a study to investigate the influence of economic recession on the management of public secondary schools in Rivers State. Results obtained showed that economic recession negatively influences social activities as well as the teaching-learning process, laying off of teachers in public schools is not the best option to elevate the effect of economic recession on public senior secondary schools. Yenle (2017) opined that the economic recession experienced in Nigeria also led to a decrease in the recruitment of teachers and other personnel needed for effective education curriculum delivery. The scholar further stated that there was massive retrenchment in schools especially private ones where parents cannot afford payment. No meaningful teaching and learning can

take place where school buildings and laboratories are dilapidated or are in dire need of urgent attention from stakeholders.

Ochai and Ogwa (2018) studied how the economic downturn affected the administration of public secondary schools in the state of Benue. The study's findings also showed that personnel management in secondary schools is impacted by the current economic climate. Obiakor (2021) did a study on how inflation and the recession are affecting secondary school students' education in Enugu State's Oji River Educational Zone. Findings showed that the economic downturn significantly increased the number of unemployed, the cost of living, the budget deficit, bond rates on the rise, and other hardships for the populace. It also significantly increased the amount of poor quality and ineffective secondary school instruction.

Constant students' enrolment in schools

It is the core function of school administration to ensure constant enrolment of students into different forms of education in Nigeria. The function is affected by economic hardship in Nigeria that has made many parents not have the capacity to send their wards to schools due to inflation, high unemployment and low income. Parental socio-economic status is a powerful predictor of children's academic attainment In Nigeria. Studies have shown that millions of parents with children in school are battling with unpaid salaries, half salaries, partial shutdown of plants, retrenchments, higher fuel, food and transportation charges, unemployment and low levels of industrial production and productivity (Sobowale, 2016). United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], (2009) research observed that the current state of economic crisis will almost affect enrollments in Nigeria and Benue State in particular and may even undo recent progress achieved toward the elusive goal of universal primary school completion. Where students incur some direct schooling costs, however small, poorer students may have to forego schooling. And since the crisis could lead to tighter credit markets, households and schools have had fewer resources to buffer themselves, and students, especially in universities, may not be able to obtain the student loans necessary to stay enrolled. Additionally, the need for kids to work outside the home and for children and youth to replace adults in home production may rise as more household members feel the obligation to make a living. Due to these consequences, there may be a decline in student performance and an increase in dropout rates.

Ogunode and Ukozor (2023) discovered that inflation has led to an increment in students dropping out; an increment in the operational cost of running universities, an increment in the cost of infrastructure facilities provision, an increment in the cost of teaching program implementation, an increment in the cost of research programme implementation and an increment in cost of community programme implementation and increment in universities fees. Furtherance to the above, OECD (2016); and OECD (2018) discovered that inflation, economic recession and economic hardship have led to a

reduction in student enrolment in schools. Inflation brings hardship, a consequence that hurts everybody in society, including students. This is why scholars have argued that inflation has direct and indirect consequences on the performance of students in secondary school (Ukozor, Ayeni & Andeshi, 2024)

Quality of education

Another responsibility of educational administration is to ensure quality education in all schools. The economic hardship in Nigeria tends to affect the quality of education in school because the human and materials resources needed to ensure the attainment of quality education are grossly provided due to inflation and this affects the quality of the system. Oladipupo and Oluwole (2008) carried out a study titled Inflation and Educational Performance in Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that inflation hurts the educational performance of school-going adolescents in Nigeria. It was found that the higher the inflation rate, the lower the educational performance of students. Okeke and Nwankwo (2011) carried out a study titled Inflation and educational performance in Nigeria at the Federal University of Technology Owerri, Imo state, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant negative relationship between inflation and educational performance in Nigeria. The study concluded that inflation affects educational performance in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY(METODOLOGIYA)

Infrastructure facilities development

The obligation to protect the economy lies in infrastructure that can boost development to enhance financial security where people can provide for their basic needs (Ayeni, 2024). The above development is because infrastructural development provides a suitable environment (Ayeni, Abdullahi & Andeshi, 2021). The importance of infrastructure in enhancing the well-being of the people led to a consensus among people of the developed world to agree that governance is the provision of infrastructure that empowers in addition to enhancing the well-being of the individuals (Ayeni & Sani, 2021; Ayeni, Sani, Idris & Uzoigwe, 2019; Ayeni, 2017). The foregoing is affirmed by scholars. Who noted that infrastructural facilities aid the delivery of academic and non-academic services in educational institutions (Ogunode, 2020). The above observation is corroborated by scholars who argue that infrastructural development enhances human security (Ayeni, Andeshi & Uzoigwe, 2022). These infrastructural facilities include; libraries, laboratories, halls, offices, administrative blocks, hostels, road facilities, water, electricity, internet et cetera. The availability of infrastructural facilities in adequate quantities will support effective administration of educational institutions and the inadequacies will prevent effective administration of educational institutions.

However, the study conducted by Ogunode, Cletus, and Tswenji, (2024a) revealed that inflation affected the running of the universities in Nigeria by increasing operational costs. The result also indicated that inflation affected project completion, and led to project abandonment, poor project financing and poor project maintenance. The findings on the impact of the economic recession on funding of secondary school education revealed that the recession affected the provision of instructional materials and infrastructure, school renovation and maintenance was difficult and education allocation in the budget was reduced. The study concluded that the economic recession has impacted negatively on education in Southwestern Nigeria (Echor & Lohor, 2022). Owing to the negative impact of inflation on infrastructural development, scholars have argued that the failure of governments to provide basic infrastructure is a threat to human security (Ayeni, Sani & Haruna, 2023; Ayeni, 2018; Muhammed & Ayeni, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION(NATIJALAR VA MUHOKAMA)

The paper revealed that economic hardship in Nigeria has affected educational administration in Nigeria by increasing the operational costs of running educational institutions across the country. The paper disclosed that economic hardship has affected the running of schools, led to a drop in budgetary allocation to schools, led to a reduction in the provision of educational resources, affected recruitment of teachers, student enrolment in schools, quality of education and infrastructure facilities development in schools across the country.

Implication for Decision-Making for Sustainable Education Development

The findings of this study indicated that economic hardship has affected the running of schools, led to a drop in budgetary allocation to schools, led to a reduction in the provision of educational resources, affected recruitment of teachers, student enrolment in schools, quality of education and infrastructure facilities development in schools across the country. Based on the foregoing, school administrators both public and private should look out of the box to find alternative ways of improving the internally generated revenue of the schools by engaging in some commercial activities.

CONCLUSION(XULOSA)

This paper assessed the impact of economic hardship on education in Nigeria. The paper concluded that economic hardship in Nigeria has affected educational administration in Nigeria by increasing the operational costs of running educational institutions across the country. The paper disclosed that economic hardship has affected the running of schools, led to a drop in budgetary allocation to schools, led to a reduction in the provision of educational resources, affected recruitment of teachers, students' enrolment in schools,

quality of education and infrastructure facilities development in schools across the country.

Based on the findings of this study, the paper recommends that the government should diversify the economy by increasing local production and providing tax holidays for schools and private investors. The government should provide loan facilities for private schools. The government should provide palliative for underprivileged Nigerians to enable them to support the schooling of their wards.

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